

ANALYSIS AND TESTING OF SANDWICH BEAMS WITH CARBON FOAM CORE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

To study suitability of emerging ultralightweight carbon foams in load-carrying structures, state-of-the-art carbon foams from various manufacturers were evaluated as core material in a sandwich construction. Sandwich beams with laminated composite facesheets with various layups were fabricated with the carbon foam core and tested under static and fatigue four-point bending loads. The beams under the static loadings showed nearly linear elastic behavior until the maximum failure loads, and then postfailed either in the yielding or the brittle mode. Initial failure occurred in the carbon foam core in a shear mode. The sandwich beams with the carbon foam cores tiled together in the middle of the beam exhibited nearly identical load-displacement behavior as well as the shear failure mode to those of the beam made with an intact core. Central displacement and strain measurements at the gauge locations matched well with the analytical solution from a sandwich-beam theory. The shear moduli and strength of the carbon foams calculated from the four-point bending tests were in good agreement with those from torsional tests if the facesheets had sufficient bending rigidity. The sandwich beams with hole-drilled carbon foam cores were fabricated and tested for an efficient weight reduction scheme for the sandwich structures. Sandwich beams with carbon foam cores survived after a few hundred or even a few hundred thousand cyclic loads. Both the moduli and strength of the beams remained nearly unchanged after the fatigue loads.

KEY WORDS: Sandwich, Carbon foam, Compressive and shear tests, Four-point bending, Static and fatigue.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon foam is emerging as an ultralightweight and efficient thermal management material for many multifunctional applications, such as high-density electronics, hybrid diesel-electric vehicles, communication satellites, and advanced aircraft. Carbon foam was shown to exhibit numerous unique properties that make it an attractive material for use in low-cost, lightweight, insulating or energy-absorbing structural components. The unique properties include tailorable thermal conductivity, low coefficient of thermal expansion, low moisture absorption and high corrosion resistance. The carbon foam is generally stiffer than other foams of the same density and is more isotropic than honeycombs. The carbon foam is easily machined and provides a large surface area for bonding as well. Open cell foams allow for vented core construction. To further study suitability of the carbon foams in load-carrying structures, the state-of-the-art/developmental carbon foams from various manufacturers were evaluated as core materials in a sandwich construction. Sandwich beams were fabricated with the carbon foam cores and loaded under static and cyclic four-point bending modes.

EXPERIMENT

Sandwich beams with laminated composite facesheets were fabricated with the carbon foam core material from various manufacturers (MER Corporation, Touchstone Research Laboratory, POCO) for the experiment. Table 1 lists compressive and shear properties (modulus and strength) as well as

densities of the various carbon foams. These modulus and strength properties were obtained from cubic specimens under compressive loading and torsional cylindrical specimens under torsional loading [1], respectively. Top and bottom laminated composites facesheets were fabricated with Cytec CYCOM IM7/5250-4 prepreg [2]. With a T012802 foam core, four different layups of [0/90/0], [90/0/90], [0/90]_s and [0/90]_{2s} facesheets were used, and their thicknesses were 0.4318 mm (0.017 in.), 0.4318 mm (0.017 in.), 0.5842 mm (0.023 in.) and 1.6 mm (0.064 in.), respectively. The layup of [0/90]_{2s} facesheet used for the other carbon foam core. The carbon foam cores were bonded with the facesheets with FM73 adhesive. The sandwich beams were loaded under four-point bending load, as shown in Figure 1. The lengths between load pins (a) and support pins (L) were 76.2 mm (3 in.) and 152.4 mm (6 in.), respectively. The load was applied with a constant displacement rate of 0.25 mm/min (0.01 in./min). Strain gauges were attached on the top and bottom of the facesheets. An extensometer measured a displacement in the middle of the bottom facesheet. Figure 2 shows one of the sandwich beam test specimens with the attached strain gauges.

Table 1 Density, compressive and shear properties of various carbon foams.

Carbon Foam ID	Density [g/cc]	Compressive		# of Specimens	Std. dev./Average		Shear		# of Specimens	Std. dev./Average	
		Modulus [MPa]	Strength [MPa]		Modulus [%]	Strength [%]	Modulus [MPa]	Strength [MPa]		Modulus [%]	Strength [%]
P100101-Bot	0.65	509.8	2.8	3	34.99%	7.87%	550.0	1.5	1	—	—
P100101-Mid	0.44	211.0	1.0	3	9.18%	6.45%	175.0	0.8	1	—	—
P100101-Top	0.25	46.7	0.4	3	37.80%	5.13%	27.3	0.3	1	—	—
M012802	0.71	2725.2	39.7	8	2.68%	14.73%	1368.4	5.7	4	7.71%	9.34%
M022102	0.67	2424.9	32.2	12	5.17%	8.40%	1427.5	6.4	4	3.20%	6.34%
T021802	0.45	379.4	4.4	3	7.52%	10.41%	587.9	2.9	3	2.78%	11.67%

Figure 1 Test configuration for tiled and un-tiled sandwich beams under four-point bending loads.

Figure 2 Sandwich beam test specimen with attached strain gauges.

1. Sandwich beams under four-point static loading

Load-displacement and load-strain curves in Figure 3 under the four-point static loading exhibited nearly linear behavior up to the maximum loads. Regardless of the layups of the facesheets, all beams failed in a shear mode in the foam core at the maximum loads, and the shear failure created cracks between the load and support spans at a nearly 45° angle, as shown in Figure 4. The load-deflection curves for the beams with carbonized foam cores (labeled with C) showed brittle behavior after the maximum failure load with several sharp peaks and valleys as the displacement kept increasing

beyond the maximum load, whereas those with graphitized foam cores (P100101-sw1B-G) showed yield-like behavior after the maximum failure loads caused by continuous crushing.

The M012802 carbon foam block was cut into two half-size blocks in the longitudinal direction. The two blocks were tiled together in the middle of the beam, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 3 shows that the tiled beam (M012802-sw02st-C-tiled) exhibited nearly identical load-displacement and load-strain curves to those of the beam with the intact core (M012802-sw02-C). All beams failed in the same shear modes in the foam core with the fracture cracks between the load and support spans at the nearly 45° angle. Therefore, the split of the foam core in the middle of the beams does not have significant influence on the behavior of the sandwich beams.

Figure 3 Displacement and strain history of sandwich beams with carbon foam cores under four-point bending loads.

Figure 4 Shear failure mode due to shear stress in the carbon foam core.

The central displacement and strain measurements at the gauge locations were compared with the solution from a sandwich-beam theory. The maximum loads in the load-displacement curves were considered as critical damage loads. For simplicity, we made an assumption that the material properties of the foam were unchanged until the critical damage was reached. Therefore, the numerical result was valid only for the elastic stage of the loadings. Another simplifying assumption made in the numerical calculation was that the carbon foam core is a homogeneous orthotropic material, and the tensile modulus is the same as the compressive modulus. The maximum displacement in the middle of the span is calculated by a theoretical formula [3]:

$$\delta = \delta_{bending} + \delta_{shear} = \frac{11PL^3}{768D} + \frac{PL}{8(GA)_{eq}}, \quad (1)$$

where P is the total applied load, and L is the length of the support span. The bending rigidity (D) and shear rigidity $(GA)_{eq}$ are calculated as follows:

$$D = \frac{E_f w t_f t_d^2}{2} + \frac{E_f w t_f^3}{6} + \frac{E_c w t_c^3}{12} \quad \text{and} \quad (GA)_{eq} = G_c \frac{w t_d^2}{t_c}, \quad (2)$$

where $t_d = t_f + t_c$. The symbols denoted are the width of the beam (w), thickness of facesheet (t_f), thickness of core (t_c), effective Young's modulus of facesheets (E_f), Young's modulus of core (E_c) and shear modulus of core (G_c). The measured compressive Young's modulus of the carbon foams was used for E_c . The top and bottom strains on the facesheets in the middle of the span are calculated by

$$\varepsilon_x = \pm \frac{M t_t / 2}{D} = \pm \frac{P L t_t}{16 D}, \quad (3)$$

where t_t is the total thickness of the sandwich beam, and M is a bending moment acting on the middle of the beam. Meanwhile, the maximum shear stress occurring in the middle of the foam core in the thickness direction is approximated by $\tau_c = P/2 w t_d$.

Figure 5 compares the measured and calculated slopes of the load-displacement and load-strain curves in the linear region. The theoretical calculation of both the displacements and strains agrees well with the measured ones for all the specimens within an approximately 10% error margin, with one exception with one of the M022102 specimens. We observed that this specimen had a significantly big void located under one of the loading pins, which resulted in a lower slope of the load-displacement curve. However, this void did not contribute much to the error in the slope of the load-strain curve.

Figure 5 Measured and calculated slopes of the load-displacement and load-strain curves of sandwich beams with various carbon foam cores under four-point loadings.

As in Eqs. (1)-(3), the central displacements (δ) are dependent both on E_f and G_c , whereas the central strains (ε_x) are independent of G_c , since no shear force exists between the load spans, and only the pure bending moment contributes to the central strains. Therefore, it is possible to calculate the shear moduli (G_c) by measuring both the deformation and strains under the four-point bending tests. Furthermore, since all the sandwich beam specimens failed in shear modes in the foam cores, the shear stress at the failure load can be considered as the shear strength of the foam core (S_c).

Figure 6 shows a comparison of the shear properties of the carbon foams measured from the torsional tests [1] and the present four-point bending tests. In the figure, the sandwich specimens were labeled with (-z) and (-y) when the sandwich beams were made by bonding the facesheets to the top and bottom surfaces of the carbon foam in the through-the-thickness (z-) and in-planar (y-) directions, respectively, while the beam span is denoted as the x-direction. The former specimens yield the shear properties of G_{xz} and S_{xz} , while the latter yield G_{yz} and S_{yz} . Both the shear modulus and strength from the sandwich beam specimens with the $[0/90]_{2s}$ layout of the facesheets agree well with those measured from the torsional tests. The error may be due to the scatter of the test data. However, it is important to note that the torsional tests yielded coupled shear properties of a combination of two planes (e.g., x-z and x-y planes), while the sandwich beam tests yielded uncoupled ones of only one plane (e.g., x-z plane). Therefore, discrepancies between two test results are expected with the anisotropic carbon foam cores.

Furthermore, the sandwich beams of T021802 carbon foam core with different layouts of facesheets result in different shear properties, which may be caused by the difference in the load-carrying capability of the facesheet. For example, the facesheets with the low bending rigidity (e.g., $[90/0/90]$) might not carry the bending load significantly so that the local stress concentration near the loading and the support pins might be transferred to the carbon foam core. In this case, the stress concentration near the pins might cause higher shear stress than the maximum shear stress occurring in the middle of the foam core in the thickness direction, which resulted in the low shear strength, as shown in Figure 6 (b). This local stress concentration can be alleviated with the other layouts with higher bending rigidities by having more 0° plies. Therefore, the facesheets with sufficient bending rigidities must be used to obtain reasonable shear properties with the sandwich beam test.

Figure 6 Comparison of shear properties of various carbon foams measured from torsional [1] and four-point bending tests.

2. Sandwich beams with hole-drilled foam core

One of the important roles of the core material in the sandwich structures is to provide sufficient shear rigidity and strength. Meanwhile, the lightweight foams are desirable for an optimal lightweight structural design. Gibson and Ashby [4] showed that the shear properties of the carbon foams change quadratically with the density variations. Therefore, the shear properties of the foam cores reduce quadratically with low-density foams if the foam possesses the same material properties in the ligaments and cell walls. Another way of reducing the weight of the foam core is to physically remove the core material, not by changing the bulk density of the foam. Drilling holes in the foam core before bonding the facesheets is one way of achieving the material removal.

Sandwich beams were fabricated with the hole-drilled carbon foam cores and tested under the four-point bending load. The effective shear moduli of the drilled foam cores were then calculated by the method of comparison of displacement and strain measurement with Eqs. (1) and (3), as suggested earlier in this study. Two different rows of arrays of holes were drilled with four different diameters with a diamond-core drill in a milling machine. For the one-row array of holes, eight holes were drilled at the centers in 25.4 mm by 25.4 mm squares with the diameters of 12.7 mm ($\frac{1}{2}$ in.) and 19.1 mm ($\frac{3}{4}$ in.). For the two-row array of holes, 32 holes were drilled at the centers in 12.7 mm by 12.7 mm squares with the diameters of 6.4 mm ($\frac{1}{4}$ in.) and 9.5 mm ($\frac{3}{8}$ in.). The smaller and larger diameters of holes for both rows of the array yield the volume ratios of $v_r = 0.804$ and 0.558, respectively. Two duplicates of the sandwich beams were made for each parameter.

Figure 7 shows the central load-displacement curves of sandwich beams with the hole-drilled carbon foam cores under the four-point bending load. The sandwich beams with the same volume ratio behaved nearly identically regardless of the number of rows of the hole array. The load-displacement curves show nearly linearly elastic behavior up to the maximum loads, and several sharp peaks and valleys, as the displacement kept increasing beyond the maximum load. The beams no longer failed in the shear modes, which would have created fractures between the load and support spans at the nearly 45° angle. Rather, the cracks were nearly vertical (parallel to the thickness direction). As the load increased, the number of cracks increased instead of one dominant crack propagating along the interface. Seen at the free edges, the locations of the cracks in the span direction were near the center of the circular holes, where cell-wall thickness after the hole-out was minimal. One thing to note is that the cracks still occurred only between the load and support spans, but not in the central region between the two load spans. Therefore, if the carbon foam cores were drilled only in the central region, but not in the loaded regions, we might expect to have the shear failure modes, which created fractured cracks between the load and support spans at the nearly 45° angle. This may suggest a way of weight reduction of the sandwich structures without sacrificing much strength property of the core material by drilling holes in less-critically loaded regions.

Figure 7 Load-displacement history of sandwich beams with hole-drilled carbon foam cores with two different volume ratios under four-point bending loads.

Figure 8 shows a variation of relative shear moduli (G^{**}/G^*) and shear strength (S^{**}/S^*) of the hole-drilled carbon foam core material against relative densities (ρ^{**}/ρ^*). The superscripts (**) and (*) represent the properties of the carbon foam cores with and without the holes, respectively. The relative density is nothing but the volume ratio (v_r). The dotted lines in the figures represent the quadratic shear property variation of the intact carbon foams with respect to the density of the foams. The sandwich beams with the carbon foam core with one row of the rectangular array of holes were

simulated numerically by a finite element analysis with a commercial finite element package, ANSYS. Under the simulated four-point bending load, the effective shear moduli of the drilled foam cores were then calculated by the method of comparison of displacement and strain measurement with Eqs. (1) and (3), and the results were plotted with a solid line in the figure of the shear moduli (Figure 8 (a)). The numerical prediction of the effective shear modulus of the holed carbon foam core agrees well with the experimental data, except in the case of 2 rows of 9.5 mm ($\frac{3}{8}$ in.) diameter hole array. In this case, the data yielded slightly lower moduli than the prediction. However, it should be noted that the large diameters of holes caused the wall-thickness of the remaining material to become so thin that the extra materials were chipped out at the exit side of the core drill during machining. Obviously, the material variation is another factor to cause the discrepancy. Nevertheless, it is clearly shown in the figure that the effective shear moduli of the hole-drilled foam cores decrease more slowly with respect to the decrease in the density than those of the intact base material. Therefore, from the modulus point of view, the hole-drilling with the high-density foams is a better way of achieving the weight reduction in the sandwich construction than using the low-density foams.

In the aspect of the shear strength, however, the quadratic line of the material behavior lies above the experimental data. This was expected since the drilled holes caused stress concentration in the thinned walls of the foam core. In the case of $\nu_r = 0.558$, the effective shear strength almost recovered to the quadratic variation. Since the analytical formulation is not available for the strength properties, it is not easy to conclude how much the strength is influenced by removing the materials. However, as stated earlier, if the materials were removed in the noncritically loaded area (e.g., central section of the beams under the four-point bending), the weight reduction can successfully be achieved without sacrificing much strength property of the core materials.

Figure 8 Relative shear moduli and strength of hole-drilled carbon foams against relative density of the foams.

3. Sandwich beams under four-point fatigue loading

The sandwich beams with the carbon foam cores were loaded under cyclic four-point bending loads. Under the fatigue loading, the beams were loaded from zero to a preset load level, so that the stress ratio, which is the ratio of minimum stress to maximum stress, was zero. A few hundred (100-500) cycles of loads were applied at low frequency levels (0.01-0.05 Hz). When the specimens survived after a few hundred cycles of loads, they were tested under static loadings to ultimate failure to obtain residual stiffness and strength of the sandwich beams.

Figure 9 shows load-displacement hysteresis of a fatigued sandwich specimen (M012802-sw6B) at various load levels. At first, the beam was loaded for a hundred cycles at 0.01 Hz to an approximately 60% load level of the maximum failure load under the static four-point loadings, as shown in Figure 9

(a). The maximum static load was taken as 4137 N (930 lbf). As the hysteresis remained unchanged after 100 cycles of loads, the load level was increased by 10% until the beam failed. At these increased load levels, the load frequency was increased to 0.05 Hz to expedite the tests. Figure 9 (b) - (e) shows the hysteresis at load levels of 70%, 80%, 90% and 100% of the static maximum load. Because of the material variation, the specimen survived after 100 cycles at 100% of load level. At all load levels, the hystereses remain unchanged after 100 cycles of loadings, which indicates that the carbon foam as the core material in the sandwich construction sustains the material properties substantially under the repeated loading conditions. The specimen ultimately failed at the second cycle of 110% of load level (Figure 9 (f)). Note that since the specimen failed at the second cycle, the test at the first cycle can be considered as residual stiffness/strength tests.

(a) $P_{max} = 2491$ N (560 lbf)

(b) $P_{max} = 2896$ N (651 lbf)

(c) $P_{max} = 3309$ N (744 lbf)

(d) $P_{max} = 3723$ N (837 lbf)

(e) $P_{max} = 4137$ N (930 lbf)

(f) $P_{max} = 4551$ N (1023 lbf)

Figure 9 Load-displacement hysteresis of a sandwich beam with M012802-sw06B carbon foam core under four-point cyclic bending loads at various load levels.

Another sandwich specimen (M012802-sw06T) was loaded at 0.05 Hz to the approximately 80% load level. The hysteresis remained unchanged after 100 cycles of loads. The specimens were tested at the same load level at a higher frequency of 0.5 Hz. The specimens survived over 130,000 cycles of loads. The specimen was then loaded under the monotonically increased static loading until ultimate failure, which provides residual stiffness and strength of the fatigued specimen. As shown in Figure 3, the load-displacement and the load-strain curves of the residual static test with M012802-sw06T differed from those of the static tests with M012802-sw02 only by the slopes of the curves because of the thickness difference of the foam cores. Furthermore, the maximum failure loads show no difference within the scatter range, which indicates that the carbon foam has substantial fatigue resistance after a few hundred thousands of the applied cyclic loading condition.

The tiled sandwich specimen (M012802-sw04st) was loaded for 100 cycles of loads at 0.05 Hz to the 80% load level. The specimen was then loaded at the same frequency up to the 90% load level. The specimen ultimately failed after 27 cycles at this load level. Since the applied load level was close to the static failure load, the unexpected early failure may be caused by the material variation. The fatigue behavior of the tiled sandwich beam indicates that initial vertical cracks in the carbon foam core may not have significant influence on the performance of the sandwich construction under this loading condition, since the strength of the foam core was much weaker than that of both the facesheets and the adhesive bonding. Along with the hole-drilled cores, the tiled foam core can be considered for the optimal sandwich construction by reducing the weight, if the strong foams of generally high density were placed in the heavily loaded area while the weak foams of low density were placed in less-critically loaded areas (such as the midsection between the two load spans).

Figure 10 shows the slopes of load-displacement curves (P/δ) and the maximum failure loads (P_{max}) of sandwich beams with various carbon foam cores under residual static tests. The values were normalized by those obtained under static tests. Both the moduli and strength of the beams remain nearly unchanged after a few hundred or even a few hundred thousand cyclic loads. Therefore, the carbon foam is definitely a good candidate for the structural applications undergoing the fatigue loadings.

Figure 10 Slopes of load-displacement curves (P/δ) and maximum failure loads (P_{max}) of sandwich beams with various carbon foam cores under residual static tests normalized by those obtained under static tests.

SUMMARY

Sandwich beams with laminated composite facesheets were fabricated with the carbon foam core and tested under static and fatigue four-point bending loads. The beams under the static loadings showed nearly linear-elastic behavior until the maximum failure loads, and then postfailed either in the

yielding or in the brittle mode. The initial failure occurred in the core material in the shear mode. The sandwich beams with the carbon foam cores tiled together in the middle of the beam exhibited nearly identical load-displacement and load-strain curves as well as the same shear failure modes to those of the beams with the intact cores.

The central displacement and strain measurements at the gauge locations matched well with the analytical solution from the sandwich-beam theory. Shear modulus of the foam core in the sandwich construction can be calculated from the slopes of the load-displacement and load-strain curves measured at the center of the beams under the four-point bending load. Furthermore, the shear stress at the failure load can be considered as the shear strength of the foam core, since the shear failure in the foam cores was the only damage mode in the present sandwich construction. The shear moduli and strength of the various carbon foams calculated in this method were in good agreement with experimental measurements by torsional tests of the foam specimens. The sandwich beam tests yielded the uncoupled shear properties of only one plane (e.g., x-z plane or x-y plane), while the torsional tests yielded the coupled ones of the combination of two planes (e.g., x-z and x-y planes). Therefore, this sandwich beam test technique is useful for the determination of the foam shear properties. However, to obtain reasonable shear properties, the local stress concentration in the foam core material must be alleviated by having the facesheets with sufficient bending rigidity.

The sandwich beams with hole-drilled carbon foam cores were fabricated and tested for an efficient weight reduction scheme for the sandwich structures. From the modulus point of view, the hole-drilling with the high-density foams is a better way of achieving the weight reduction in the sandwich construction than using the low-density foams. If the materials were removed in the noncritically loaded area (e.g., central section of the beams under the four-point bending), the weight reduction can be achieved without sacrificing much strength property of the core materials as well.

The sandwich beams with the carbon foam core survived after a few hundred or even a few hundred thousand cyclic loads. Both the moduli and strength of the beams remained nearly unchanged after the fatigue loads. Therefore, carbon foam is definitely a good candidate for the structural applications undergoing the fatigue loadings.

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